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**SAFETY MANAGEMENT IN HAZARDOUS
EMPLOYMENTS****Pradeep M. D.¹**¹Assistant Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University,
Mangaluru, Karnataka, India**Abstract**

Organization should provide safe and healthy environment to its employees. The Health and Safety Policies aims to create healthy work place by reducing hazards affecting the performance of employees. Hazardous working conditions will increase the health risks leading to high rate of absenteeism and attrition. Frequent exposure of the worker to the unhealthy working conditions slowly develops occupational diseases. Occupational hazards are the potential conditions both internal and external transforming into a series of events causing loss. Death, injuries and illness can arise out of safety violations or negligence. Safety is the protection against uncertain risks caused by the hazards of electricity, machinery, slip or trip, explosion causing injury, death or damage to people and property. This study aims to describe the fundamentals of industrial safety management for hazardous industries in India.

Keywords: Safety, Hazards, Occupation, Accident, Diseases, Negligence, damage.

1. Introduction:

Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing but not merely the absence of disease or infirmity according to the World Health Organisation. Industrial safety ensures protection against accidents and diseases occurring in the industrial establishment [1]. The basic elements of safety management covers the aspects risk, dangerous occurrences, accident, injury, disablement, Reportable Injury, Health, medical examination, occupational hazards covering chemical, biological, environmental and psychological, occupational diseases [2] prescribed under the Factories Act, 1948 vide Sections 89 and 90 [3].

2. Scope for Industrial Safety:

Accident is an unplanned and uncontrolled event resulting in an action or reaction resulting in the personal injury [4]. Disability caused by accident may be partial or total, fatal or non-fatal. Apart from mechanical failures, unsafe working conditions, ignorance and negligence of employee there could be multiple inter related causes contributing to the industrial accident [5]. The Industrial advancements are posting new dangers into the lives of workforce. The Factories act, The Indian Electricity Act, The Pesticides Act, The Boiler Act, The Environment Protection Act etc regulates the aspects of industrial safety. It is reported that in every twenty seconds of every working minute someone dies as a result of industrial accident [6]. Industrial activity exposes the employees into the threats caused by man, material and machines demands safety training to protect themselves from disabling injuries. Few causes for accident includes taking shortcuts, over confidence, incomplete instructions, poor housekeeping, ignorance, mental distraction, unplanned activities etc. Safety

programmes ensures zero physical hazards [7]. Accident Prevention is a Process to correct the unsafe working conditions in the industrial enterprises to prevent human suffering. The Bureau of Indian Standards is prescribing guidelines for recording any type of accidents [8].

3. Safety Analysis, Safety Audit & Safety Survey:

Job safety analysis is a technique to scrutinize the job tasks to identify various hazards to determine the relationship between the employee, assigned tasks, the machinery involved and the working environment to derive the possible risks. The identified uncontrolled hazards will be synthesized by reducing them to the acceptable risk level. Risk assessment is a legal requirement under regulation 3 of the Management of Health and Safety at Work, 1999 [9]. Job safety analysis is conducted for the job having highest injury rates, having high potential for severe injuries, possibility for human error is high which leads to severe accident, new processes and complex work profiles. Safety analysis conducts an observation on the each and every steps involved in the completion of assigned job to an experienced worker of the industry. The Potential hazards and unsafe acts are identified and communicated to such worker for further correction. A safety audit is a study of operations to determine actions required to render the potential hazards harmless. A safety audit is an inventory or checklists planned pertaining to an area on regular intervals to scrutinize the aspect of safety to correct the discrepancies [10]. The audit is conducted after conducting Preliminary visits to study the factory and identify audit elements, questionnaire is prepared, data is collected after discussion with the management, executives, workers etc., cross verification is performed at the site, perusal of records regarding previous accidents etc. are done, final report is prepared along with proper findings and suggestions. Safety Survey are made to have detailed observations of all types of unsafe physical and environmental conditions as well as unsafe practices committed throughout the industries. It can be done by statutory authorities, third parties or by internal personnel. Safety and health surveys in factories are conducted by CIF (Chief Inspector of Factories), DGFASILI (Director General of Factory Advisory Service and Labour Institute), Director of Health Services of Government of India or by anyone authorized by the above authorities

4. Safety Management:

Comprehensive Safety Approach should focus on revision of engineering, employee proneness, training, persuasion, appeal, discipline, design, construction, maintenance and operational procedures. As Prevention is better than cure, following measures can be taken to protect employee against occupational health hazards. It is recommended to conduct Pre-employment Medical examination, Periodic Post-employment Medical examination, Removal of hazardous conditions to the possible extent, Surveillance over special classes of workers including women and children, Emergency treatment in case of accidents, education of workers, first aid Training, Proper factory layout and illumination, effluent treatment plants, redesigning the job to eliminate monotony and fatigue and rescheduling of work etc. The accident prevention is possible through management efforts, safety measures, safety education, on the job training, publicity, safety inspections, safety audit, spot checking, inspection, enforcement, safety policy, safety committee, government support, feedback mechanisms etc.

5. Conclusion:

Industries are mostly concerned about cutting costs on all fronts to remain competitive instead of protecting the lives of workers. The ever increasing Mechanization, Electrification, Chemicalisation and sophistication have made industrial jobs more and more complex and intricate. This has led to increased dangers to human life in industries through accidents and injuries. An accident does not only result in the stoppage of work of a particular unit but disturbs the entire environment. It causes disturbance in the work pattern and tempo which is far more than the actual time loss or direct cost of an accident. Sometimes there is an erroneous notion that safety precautions are not compatible with higher productivity but, where managements have taken pain to reduce accidents which will increase the productivity and build industrial relations. In the twenty first century employee safety and health at work has grabbed the attention of psychologists who are concerned with controlling accidents through proper training and education of the workforce. It also focuses towards controlling the social and psychological factors that influence the workers behavior which lead for negligence at work place. Industrial stress caused by various Stressors such as task and role demands, organizational leadership, lack of group cohesion, intergroup and interpersonal conflicts, life and career changes, etc., lead to emotional disturbances which, in turn, lead to fatigue and exhaustion. All these affect health of employees. Safety responsibility is upon the shoulders of Plant Manager, production Manager, Chief Engineer, Personnel Manager, and Safety officer. In the twenty first century employee safety and health at work has grabbed the attention of psychologists who are concerned with controlling accidents through proper training and education of the workforce. It also focuses towards controlling the social and psychological factors that influence the workers behavior which lead for negligence at work place. It is difficult for Management to change the human nature, therefore, instead of trying to persuade employees not to make mistake try to remove opportunities for errors by changing the work situation, plant or equipment design and the method of working.

6. References:

- [1] Khanka S.S. (2005). 'Human Resource Management (Text and Cases)', Sultan Chand & Co, New Delhi, 239.
- [2] Ronald Blake (Ed.) (1963). 'Industrial Safety', Prentice Hall, New York, 300.
- [3] The Factories Act, 1948, (1977). 'Central Law Agency', Allahabad, 52.
- [4] Heinrich H.W. (1959). 'Industrial Accident Prevention', Tata Mc Graw Hill, New Delhi, 16.
- [5] Donald J. Kirpatrick (1964). 'Supervisory Inventory on Safety', Personnel Administration, 8(4), 32-34.
- [6] Aswathappa K. (1999). 'Human Resource and Personnel Management', Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Limited, New Delhi, 457.
- [7] Barenklau K.E. (1999). 'Doing the Right Things Right', Occupational Health and Safety, March
- [8] BIS Code No. 3786.
- [9] BPP Learning Media, (2009). 'Management-Business Essentials', BPP Learning Media, London, ed. p. 386.
- [10] Tripathi P.C. (2006). 'Personnel Management and Industrial Relations', Sulthan Chand and Sons Publication New Delhi, 16.5.